

The Alkaline and Acid Hydrolysis of *n*-Butylacetate in Methanol-Water Mixtures

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Alkaline and acid hydrolysis of *n*-butylacetate was carried out in aqueous methanol at 10-25° for the alkaline and at 25-50° for the acid hydrolysis. In alkaline hydrolysis, the reaction was irreversible and the bimolecular rate constants decreased steadily with progressive increase of the organic solvent in the reaction medium. In the acid hydrolysis, the reaction attained an equilibrium which depended upon the solvent composition. With progressive additions of methanol to the acidic ester solution, the overall and reverse reaction rates increased gradually while the forward reaction rate decreased. The characteristic kinetic behaviours are discussed in the light of the 'Back-Strain' effect and solvation phenomena. The effect of dielectric constant on reaction rate is interpreted by the treatment of Amis, based on simple electrostatic consideration of ion-dipole interactions. The isocomposition, isodielectric energy and logarithm of the Arrhenius frequency factor are also calculated and interpreted in terms of solvation effects. Mechanisms for alkaline and acidic hydrolyses are proposed which account for the role and the effects of the solvent on the reaction rate. The thermodynamic parameters $\Delta G^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are calculated as a support to the proposed mechanisms.

ALKALINE and acidic ester hydrolysis has been studied earlier^{1,2}. Costeanu and Mateescu³ studied the alkaline hydrolysis of *n*-butylacetate, propionate and butyrate in aqueous acetone. It was found that the rate of alkaline hydrolysis decreased with a decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium. Using acetone of mole fractions ranging from 0.124 to 0.377, the variation in the hydrolysis rate constant was found to follow the order $\text{MeCO}_2\text{Bu} > \text{EtCO}_2\text{Bu} > \text{PrCO}_2\text{Bu}$, i. e. it decreased with the decreasing dipole moment of the esters. The acid hydrolysis of butylacetate in different H_2O -acetone mixtures has been studied at 40, 50 and 60°⁴. The reaction rate constant was correlated with the dielectric constant and the viscosity of the mixed solvent. The values of the rate constants at every temperature passed through a minimum for a mole fraction of 0.4 of acetone. These data at different mole fractions of acetone permitted the calculation of the values of activation energy, frequency factor and thermodynamic parameters, which all show a maximum at the same mole fraction. The characteristic kinetic behaviours were discussed in the light of the solvation phenomena. In the present study, the alkaline and acidic hydrolysis of *n*-butylacetate in various methanol-water mixtures are investigated. The calculated thermodynamic data and other parameters are discussed as evidence supporting the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Materials: *n*-Butylacetate (B. D. H.) was further purified by drying over sodium sulphate for

24 hr followed by fractional distillation. The fraction distilling at 124-125°/760 mm was collected and used. Methanol (E. Merck) was also purified as reported in literature⁵. Conductivity water was used for the different preparations and kinetic runs.

Preparation of solutions: An appropriate amount of the organic solvent was introduced in a measuring flask containing an weighed amount of *n*-butylacetate, affording a 0.05 *M* for the alkaline and 0.1 *M* for the acid hydrolysis. After attainment of thermal equilibrium the requisite quantity of NaOH solution, corresponding to 0.05 *M* for the alkaline hydrolysis, and that of HCl solution, corresponding to 0.1 *M* for the acid hydrolysis, was added to the ester solution. The volume was then made upto the mark and the flask placed in a thermostat at a temperature held constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

Rate determination: The rate of the alkaline hydrolysis was followed by withdrawing 5 ml samples of the reaction mixture. These were allowed to flow through an ion exchanger containing the cation Amberlite resin, IR-120 (H). The liberated acetic acid was determined by titration. The estimated infinity values in methanol-water mixtures indicated that the reaction is not of the reversible type. The values of the specific velocity constant k_2 were calculated using the second-order rate equation:

$$k_2 = \frac{x}{a(a-x)t} \quad \dots (1)$$

where *a* is the initial concentration of both ester and alkali and *x* is the amount decomposed in

time t . In the acidic hydrolysis the reaction followed a first order law and was found to be of reversible nature. The rate constants were determined by titrating the liberated acetic acid with standard alkali. The effect of temperature on the position of equilibrium was investigated. No change in the equilibrium concentration was detected with change in temperature. So the infinity or equilibrium values were determined by heating the samples in sealed ampoules at 70° for 2-4 days until two successive values were identical. The rate constants k'_1 and k'_2 of the forward and backward reactions, respectively were calculated using the kinetic equation :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k'_1 (a - x_e) - k'_2 x_e \quad \dots (2)$$

The backward rate is assumed to obey a first order law, since the concentration of the acetic acid liberated by the forward reaction is small compared to the concentration of the total alcohol in the medium. Integration of equation (2) gives the expression,

$$(k'_1 + k'_2)t = 2.303 \log x_e / (x_e - x) \quad \dots (3)$$

where x_e is the equilibrium value. It follows, therefore, from equation (3) that the plot of $\log x_e / (x_e - x)$ versus t should give a straight line with a positive slope which is equal to $(k'_1 + k'_2) / 2.303$, and that :

$$k'_1 = (k'_1 + k'_2) \cdot x_e / a \quad \dots (4)$$

where a is the infinity value for the complete reaction.

Results and Discussion

1. *Effect of temperature* : Interpolated values of k_2 (in $l. mole^{-1} sec^{-1}$) for the alkaline hydrolysis of n -butylacetate in presence of methanol-water mixtures in the temperature range $10-25^\circ$ are given in Table 1, while the corresponding values

TABLE 1—INTERPOLATED VALUES OF k_2 (in $l. mole^{-1} sec^{-1}$) FOR THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF n -BUTYLACETATE IN PRESENCE OF METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt. % of Solvent	$10^3 k_2$			
	10°	15°	20°	25°
15	4.420	6.300	8.675	11.500
20	3.625	5.125	7.000	9.650
25	2.925	4.100	5.750	7.875
30	2.350	3.350	4.650	6.500
35	1.800	2.650	3.650	5.100
40	1.375	2.050	2.925	3.975
45	1.025	1.575	2.225	3.050
50	0.750	1.200	1.720	2.300
55	0.575	0.900	1.340	1.800
60	0.420	0.650	1.000	1.325
65	0.300	0.500	0.750	0.950
70	0.225	0.400	0.560	0.700
75	0.175	0.325	0.450	0.525
80	0.140	0.250	0.350	0.400

for the overall, forward and backward reactions, (k_{obs} , k'_1 and k'_2) respectively, for the acid hydrolysis are recorded in Table 2. Arrhenius equation is strictly obeyed. Good straight lines are obtained on plotting $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$, for alkaline hydrolysis as shown in Fig. 1. The values of the isocomposition activation energy, E_o , and frequency factor $\log A$ were calculated by the least square method and are compiled in Table 3. For the acid hydrolysis, good straight lines were obtained on plotting the $\log k'_1$ versus $1/T$. The values of the forward $E_{1,obs}$, backward $E_{2,obs}$, observed $E_{o,obs}$ activation energies, and the frequency factor $\log A$ for the forward reaction are also calculated by the least square method and recorded in Table 3. However, to obtain a more precise treatment of the results, the temperature dependence of the dielectric constant should be eliminated. This is achieved by calculating the isodielectric activation energies, E_d , from the corresponding rate constants in isodielectric solutions. The values of E_d for alkaline hydrolysis and the values of $E_{1,d}$, $E_{2,d}$ and $E_{d,obs}$ for the acid hydrolysis are given in Table 4.

TABLE 2—INTERPOLATED VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS ($k \times 10^5 sec^{-1}$) FOR THE ACID HYDROLYSIS OF n -BUTYLACETATE IN PRESENCE OF METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt % Solvent	$10^5 k$										$10^5 k'_1$	$10^5 k'_2$
	$10^5 k_{obs}$	25° $10^5 k'_1$	$10^5 k'_2$	30° $10^5 k_{obs}$	$10^5 k'_1$	$10^5 k'_2$	40° $10^5 k_{obs}$	$10^5 k'_1$	$10^5 k'_2$	$10^5 k_{obs}$		
15	1.700	0.900	0.800	2.850	1.680	1.170	6.800	3.740	3.060	14.000	7.220	6.780
20	1.800	0.815	0.985	3.000	1.560	1.440	6.900	3.380	3.520	14.400	6.920	7.480
25	1.875	0.760	1.115	3.200	1.415	1.785	7.000	3.080	3.920	15.000	6.580	8.420
30	1.900	0.705	1.195	3.350	1.290	2.060	7.100	2.850	4.250	15.800	6.270	9.530
35	2.050	0.655	1.395	3.550	1.170	2.380	7.300	2.650	4.650	17.300	5.980	11.320
40	2.175	0.610	1.565	3.750	1.067	2.683	7.650	2.500	5.150	18.600	5.690	12.910
45	2.350	0.575	1.775	4.000	0.990	3.010	8.050	2.370	5.680	20.600	5.420	15.180
50	2.550	0.547	2.003	4.250	0.925	3.325	8.700	2.280	6.420	22.900	5.180	17.720
55	2.740	0.523	2.217	4.600	0.875	3.725	9.500	2.200	7.300	25.800	4.960	20.940
60	3.000	0.505	2.495	4.950	0.835	4.115	10.600	2.140	8.460	29.200	4.750	24.450
65	3.400	0.493	2.907	5.450	0.800	4.650	13.000	2.080	10.920	33.600	4.570	29.030
70	3.875	0.487	3.388	6.200	0.775	5.425	13.600	2.040	11.560	39.000	4.430	34.570
75	4.650	0.482	4.168	7.200	0.765	6.435	15.800	2.000	13.800	46.000	4.340	41.660
80	5.725	0.475	5.250	8.550	0.760	7.790	19.600	1.980	17.620	55.800	4.275	51.525
85	7.275	0.473	6.802	10.650	0.755	9.895	25.400	1.960	23.440	69.000	4.240	64.760
90	9.250	0.470	8.780	13.750	0.750	13.000	33.800	1.950	31.850	83.400	4.200	79.200

Fig. 1. Determination of activation energy in methanol-water mixtures.

 TABLE 3—ISOCOMPOSITION ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION (in Kcal mole⁻¹) AND FREQUENCY FACTORS IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt. % solvent	Alkaline hydrolysis		Acid hydrolysis			
	E_c	$\log A$	E_{1c}	E_{2c}	E_c obs.	$\log A$
15	10.69	9.90	15.67	19.34	16.12	12.48
20	10.89	9.96	15.99	15.75	15.84	12.67
25	11.09	10.03	16.16	15.38	15.71	12.75
30	11.29	10.08	16.40	15.55	15.88	12.90
35	11.55	10.17	16.67	15.58	15.90	13.05
40	11.87	10.31	16.91	15.65	16.02	13.20
45	12.13	10.39	17.05	15.87	16.18	13.27
50	12.49	10.53	17.16	16.18	16.41	13.33
55	12.82	10.67	17.23	16.66	16.75	13.36
60	13.01	10.68	17.22	17.04	17.08	13.38
65	12.98	10.52	17.17	17.49	17.45	13.28
70	12.58	10.10	17.08	17.43	17.40	13.21
75	12.20	9.71	17.00	17.34	17.31	13.14
80	11.70	9.22	16.98	17.22	17.30	13.13
85	—	—	16.95	17.17	17.26	13.10
90	—	—	16.93	16.95	16.95	13.08

 TABLE 4—ISODIELECTRIC ACTIVATION ENERGIES (in Kcal mole⁻¹) FOR METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

D	Alkaline hydrolysis		Acid hydrolysis	
	E_d	E_{1d}	E_{2d}	E_d obs.
40	—	17.34	9.19	13.86
50	18.54	17.79	12.91	14.40
55	18.23	—	—	—
60	17.61	18.00	12.98	14.40
65	17.25	—	—	—
70	16.59	13.37	13.37	14.29

Both the velocity constants in the alkaline hydrolysis and the forward reaction for the acid hydrolysis are found to decrease with the progressive addition of methanol. This trend is ascribed to the decrease of water concentration as well as to the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium. On the other hand, the isocomposition activation energy, E_c , increases to a maximum value for both alkaline and acidic hydrolysis, while isodielectric activation energies, E_d , increase with the decrease of the dielectric constant in alkaline hydrolysis and pass through maximum in case of acid hydrolysis. This may be due to the solvation of the activated complex to a less extent than that of the reactants. Although the changes in $\log A$ are generally more sensitive to solvent composition, the variation of the activation energy with solvent composition is more pronounced than that of $\log A$.

Thermodynamic data of the activated complex :

The effect of changes in solvent composition on the rate constant of the reaction is conveniently verified in terms of the thermodynamic parameters of activation. These are calculated at different temperatures for different solvent composition in both alkaline and acidic hydrolysis and are compiled in Tables 5 and 6.

In both alkaline and acidic hydrolysis, the data of ΔG^* indicate that solvation of the reactants is more than that of the activated complex which is in agreement with the decrease of the bimolecular rate constant in alkaline hydrolysis and the forward rate constant in acidic hydrolysis as the concentration of the methanol in the mixture increases. The heat content change ΔH^* , shows a maximum in both alkaline and acidic hydrolysis. This may be a direct consequence of the behaviour of the isocomposition activation energy with the increasing organic solvent content. The non-linear relation between ΔS^* and the solvent composition in alkaline and acidic media indicate specific solvation and hence a non-random distribution of the solvent molecules⁹.

Effect of dielectric constant : Akerlof's data⁹ are used to obtain the dielectric constant values for the mixtures under investigation by interpolation. For the alkaline hydrolysis, the plots of $\log k_2$ against $1/D$ (Fig. 2) give straight lines with negative slopes. Deviations from this linearity are observed at high solvent concentration (region of low dielectric constant). These deviations are probably due to the preferential solvation of the activated complex by water, the higher dielectric constant component. Consequently the distribution of the solvent molecules will be less random, and the values of D in the immediate vicinity of the ion will diverge considerably from that in the bulk, which is the value measured experimentally. This effect becomes larger as the dielectric constant becomes lower. In the acidic hydrolysis, an increase of the dielectric constant of the mixtures is found to lead to an increase in the rate of the forward reaction. However, the rate of the overall and reverse

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES ΔG^* AND ΔH^* IN KCAL/MOLE, ΔS^* IN CAL/MOLE/DEGREE

Wt % Solvent	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80
10° ΔG^*	18.300	18.412	18.532	18.655	18.805	18.957	19.122	19.298	19.448	19.624	19.814	19.976	20.117	20.243
10° ΔH^*	10.130	10.325	10.529	10.725	10.935	11.308	11.570	11.939	12.261	12.449	12.418	12.021	11.636	11.137
10° $-\Delta S^*$	28.854	28.561	28.264	28.006	27.618	27.014	26.671	26.035	25.382	25.340	26.120	28.095	29.952	32.160
15° ΔG^*	18.430	18.548	18.676	18.792	18.926	19.073	19.224	19.380	19.545	19.731	19.881	20.009	20.128	20.278
15° ΔH^*	10.120	10.315	10.519	10.715	10.975	11.298	11.560	11.919	12.251	12.439	12.408	12.011	11.626	11.127
15° $-\Delta S^*$	28.839	28.572	28.308	28.031	27.593	26.982	26.507	25.893	25.313	25.306	25.934	27.756	29.505	31.758
20° ΔG^*	18.574	18.690	18.814	18.914	19.079	19.208	19.367	19.517	19.662	19.823	20.001	20.171	20.298	20.445
20° ΔH^*	10.110	10.305	10.509	10.906	10.965	11.289	11.550	11.909	12.241	12.429	12.398	12.001	11.616	11.117
20° $-\Delta S^*$	28.873	28.634	28.330	28.102	27.679	27.013	26.666	25.953	25.315	25.223	25.936	27.670	29.616	31.890
25° ΔG^*	18.733	18.837	18.958	19.071	19.215	19.363	19.520	19.687	19.832	20.014	20.211	20.392	20.562	20.733
25° ΔH^*	10.100	10.295	10.499	10.693	10.955	11.279	11.540	11.899	12.231	12.419	12.388	11.991	11.606	11.107
25° $-\Delta S^*$	28.955	28.650	28.372	29.090	27.701	27.114	26.765	26.121	25.491	25.474	26.338	28.177	30.039	32.252

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE ΔG^* AND ΔH^* IN KCAL/MOLE; ΔS^* IN CAL/MOLE/DEGREE

Wt % Solvent	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90
25° ΔG^*	24.389	24.397	24.439	24.483	24.527	24.569	24.604	24.634	24.660	24.681	24.695	24.703	24.709	24.717	24.720	24.724
25° ΔH^*	15.079	15.393	15.570	15.810	16.073	16.318	16.454	16.568	16.633	16.628	16.576	16.490	16.407	16.337	16.362	16.335
25° $-\Delta S^*$	31.057	30.200	29.745	29.091	23.355	27.674	27.335	27.053	26.925	27.012	27.231	27.544	27.843	27.940	28.035	28.137
30° ΔG^*	24.381	24.425	24.484	24.540	24.599	24.654	24.699	24.740	24.774	24.802	24.828	24.847	24.855	24.859	24.863	24.867
30° ΔH^*	15.069	15.383	15.560	15.800	16.063	16.303	16.444	16.558	16.623	16.618	16.566	16.480	16.397	16.377	16.352	16.325
30° $-\Delta S^*$	30.717	29.928	29.438	28.831	28.157	27.532	27.232	26.991	26.888	26.998	27.252	27.599	27.898	27.973	28.075	28.177
40° ΔG^*	24.707	24.770	24.828	24.876	24.922	24.958	24.991	25.015	25.037	25.055	25.072	25.091	25.097	25.103	25.109	25.113
40° ΔH^*	15.049	15.363	15.540	15.780	16.043	16.288	16.424	16.538	16.603	16.598	16.547	16.461	16.377	16.357	16.332	16.305
40° $-\Delta S^*$	30.841	30.039	29.658	29.048	28.352	27.686	27.357	27.070	26.935	27.006	27.226	27.539	27.844	27.928	28.039	28.126
50° ΔG^*	25.094	25.121	25.154	25.185	25.215	25.247	25.278	25.307	25.335	25.363	25.388	25.408	25.421	25.431	25.436	25.442
50° ΔH^*	15.029	15.344	15.521	15.760	16.023	16.268	16.401	16.518	16.583	16.578	16.527	16.441	16.358	16.337	16.312	16.285
50° $-\Delta S^*$	31.145	30.258	29.810	29.164	28.444	27.785	27.460	27.198	27.084	27.186	27.421	27.749	28.047	28.139	28.234	28.327

Fig. 2. Variation of k with dielectric constant in methanol-water mixtures.

reactions decrease with increasing dielectric constant. Plots of $\log k'$, against $1/D$ give straight lines with negative slopes in the high dielectric range, but deviations from linearity become evident as the dielectric constant decreases. This deviation is probably due to the preferential solvation of the activated complex by water.

Effect of solvent composition: In the alkaline hydrolysis, the rate constants are found to decrease with the decrease of water concentration in the medium. The plots of $\log k_2$ versus $\log C_w$ give straight lines having a positive slope in water-rich mixtures, followed by a curvature in the regions of solvent-rich mixtures (Fig. 3). The slopes obtained are found to vary slightly with temperature, and have a mean value of 3.15 in the water-rich mixtures. These slopes represent the number of water molecules involved in the formation of the activated complex.

The variation of the rate constant as a function of the concentration of alcohol in the solvent mixture is attributed to many factors^{10,11}, concerning the nucleophile and the substrate. It has been reported that when sodium hydroxide is dissolved in ethanol (or methanol) the solution would mainly contain ethoxide (or methoxide) rather than hydroxide ions¹²⁻¹⁴ and many puzzling facts have been explained in the light of this assumption^{15,16}.

Fig. 3. Variation of k_2 with water concentration in methanol-water mixtures.

The extensive investigations done by Brown *et al.*¹⁷ on the steric effects on equilibria were extended to the study of "back strain" effects on the basicity of alkoxide¹⁸. It was concluded that the basicity of methoxide ion is less than that of hydroxide ions. Since the rate of the reaction is dependent on the stoichiometric concentration of the base anion, it is expected that the rate will decrease due to the decrease in the stoichiometric concentration of the hydroxide ion by the addition of the organic solvent component, according to the equation :

Thus, it would not be surprising in this case that the rate constant decreases continuously by the successive addition of methanol to the reaction medium although the dielectric constant of the medium decreases.

In the acidic hydrolysis, the overall and reverse rate constants are found to increase as the water concentration in reaction medium decreases. However, the forward rate is found to decrease with decreasing water concentration. The plot of $\log k'_1$ against $\log C_w$ gives straight lines of mean value unit slope. These slopes represent the number of water molecules involved in the formation of the activated complex. The lines are straight in the range of high concentration of water but deviations from linearity become evident as the water concentration decreases.

It is clear that the decrease of the forward rate constant with the progressive addition of alcohol

is harmonic with the decrease of water concentration and the decrease of the dielectric constant of the medium, also the decrease of acidity of hydrochloric acid (the increase of basicity of water) accompanying the addition of alcohol. This has been attributed¹⁹ to the progressive breakdown of the tetrahedral structure of water. Thus, instead of having the structure $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{H}^+$ one may have the species $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{H}^+$ besides, since the proton affinity in the open structure $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{H}^+$ is less than that in the compact structure, the latter will be holding the proton more firmly and hence in the presence of alcohol, water will be more basic, and thus the net result is a decrease in rate.

Proposed mechanism : In the alkaline hydrolysis, the change in the relative concentrations of the hydroxide and alkoxide ions due to the change in the solvent composition is accommodated by the equilibrium represented by equation (5). Accordingly, the overall reaction rate may be represented by equation (6),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{Ester}] [\text{Base}] \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{where } [\text{Base}] = [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{RO}^-] \quad \dots (7)$$

accordingly, equation (6) becomes,

$$\text{Rate} = [\text{Ester}] \{k' [\text{OH}^-] + k'' [\text{RO}^-]\} \quad \dots (8)$$

Substituting for OH in equation (8) from equilibrium (5) and rearranging, we obtain,

$$\text{Rate} = [\text{Ester}] [\text{RO}^-] \left\{ \frac{k' [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K [\text{ROH}]} + k'' \right\} \quad \dots (9)$$

therefore,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k' [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K [\text{ROH}]} + k'' \quad \dots (10)$$

where k' and k'' are the specific rate constants for the reaction catalysed by OH and RO ions, respectively and K is the equilibrium constant represented by equation (5). The increase of methanol content will cause a decrease in the first term of the right hand side of equation (10) as well as in k'' due to the increase in RO concentration according to equation (5) and hence k_{obs} will also decrease.

In acidic hydrolysis the forward rate of reaction decreases with increase in the methanol concentration. It is known that¹⁹ the proton is hydrated by four water molecules and it has the structure $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{H}^+$ in the cluster shape. In mixed solvents, the net reaction actually taking place is the substitution of water by alcohol in the cluster, for example :

Hence, the following reaction mechanism is proposed.

(Fast pre-equilibrium)

where S is a solvent molecule and T⁺ stands for the solvated transition state in which the solvation is maintained through H-bonding.

Assuming a steady state approximation,

$$K'_1 [\text{Ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}^+] = K'_2 [\text{T}][\text{S}] + K_3 [\text{T}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \\ = [\text{T}]\{K'_2[\text{S}] + K_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]\} \quad \dots (14)$$

$$[\text{T}] = \frac{K'_1 [\text{Ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}^+]}{K'_2[\text{S}] + K_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad \dots (15)$$

The rate of reaction is given by

$$= K_3 [\text{T}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad \dots (16)$$

$$= \frac{K_3 K'_1 [\text{Ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}^+][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K'_2[\text{S}] + K_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad \dots (17)$$

$$= \frac{K_3 K'_1 [\text{Ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}^+]}{K'_2 \frac{[\text{S}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} + K_3} \quad \dots (18)$$

since K₃ is small in comparison to K'₂, thus the

$$\text{rate} = \frac{K'_1 K_3}{K'_2} \frac{[\text{Ester}][\text{H}_2\text{O}^+][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{S}]} \quad \dots (19)$$

This mechanism verifies the direct dependence of the rate on the water concentration and the inverse proportionality of the rate with the organic solvent concentration.

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